

Imagine transforming ten hours of meticulous meal prep, complex topic comprehension, or detailed travel planning into just two hours. This leap in efficiency, thanks to ChatGPT, an advanced artificial intelligence (AI) model, has freed up invaluable time for more meaningful activities. As a dental student preparing for the Integrated National Board Dental Exam (INBDE), I envisioned leveraging this powerful technology to revolutionize my study process. With no prior background in software development or computer engineering, I embarked on a journey to learn more about how to build my own model to enhance my studying.

GPT-4 is a type of AI technology called a large language model (LLM) that uses natural language processing (NLP) to interact with humans through its chatbot interface, ChatGPT. The platform is trained on freely available data via books, web text, articles, and other online sources up until April 2023.¹ ChatGPT allows users to create personal assistants specifically for certain tasks or purposes such as medical education. Previous studies have highlighted ChatGPT's capabilities in this realm. It achieved a 90% correlation coefficient for correct answers on the United States Medical Licensing Exam (USMLE) Steps 1, 2, 3 in a study.¹ Similarly, ChatGPT had passed a radiology board-style examination without images and showed efficacy in questions based on clinical information for oral radiology-based multiple choice questions.^{3,4} In terms of the Integrated National Board Dental Examination (INBDE), GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 answered 61.3% and 76.9% of questions accurately on average demonstrating ChatGPT 4's potential use in dental education.⁵

While prior studies have shown that GPT-4 could pass the dental exam, its ability to simulate clinical reasoning in a way that benefits students remains unknown. ChatterMouth is a GPT-4 powered chatbot that generates a multiple choice question in the style of the INDBE and prompts users for an answer. It then offers hints and explanations to guide users to the correct answer if they answer incorrectly. ChatterMouth was developed by crafting a prompt for ChatGPT that employed three prompt engineering techniques. First, we assigned the identity of the GPT ("You are a dental school professor preparing students for a board exam") and its target audience ("Dental students"). Second, we fed the model a single example of a question and answer in the format we wanted, a method called "One Shot Prompting".⁶ Third, we uploaded a document from the INBDE with background information on the types of questions included in the exam, their formatting, and some sample questions.⁷ This method is called "Retrieval Augmented Generation" or RAG which provides more context for the GPT by referencing this specific knowledge base outside of its existing trained sources (Table 1).⁸

When prompted, our first iteration of ChatterMouth was able to effectively generate a question in the correct format. However, when the user made their answer selection for the generated question, ChatterMouth's assessment of that selection and its feedback on the user's answer was often incorrect (Table 2). To mitigate these issues, we added a directive in the prompt that instructed the GPT to first work through the solution, then compare its solution to the student's response without immediately revealing the correct answer. In this technique, called "chain of thought prompting", the prompt includes step by step instructions on how the GPT should process, contextualize, and generate a response to a user's input. The use of this technique has been shown to improve accuracy and reduce hallucinations.⁹

Next, we found that GPT occasionally forgets parts of the instructions it was given. Specifically, it was revealing the correct answers to students when they answered incorrectly, instead of giving them hints to help them arrive at the correct answer as instructed in the prompt. To address this, we emphasized within the prompt multiple times that the GPT should not disclose the correct answer if the student's response is incorrect. Over time, with reinforced instructions throughout the prompt, the GPT began to improve, providing better hints and explanations throughout extended conversations. Another technique we used to improve ChatterMouth's performance was to ask it to be more concise. That this technique works is based on the principle that longer messages require more "tokens," building blocks of text that can range from characters to words. In this context, GPT-4 had a 32,000 token limit during the time we were creating ChatterMouth.¹⁰ Therefore, to limit the use of tokens, I requested ChatterMouth to use less verbose language in its explanations because shorter messages are handled more effectively by the GPT. Additionally, I came to realize that ChatterMouth performed better when asked to generate a question in a specific content area rather than when asked to generate a question without specifying a content area. This helped us realize the scope and abilities of our bot.

By creating and refining ChatterMouth, I was able to better understand the current capabilities and limitations of LLMs in education, and was able to test strategies for improving the performance of LLMs in this context. We found that a resource such as ChatterMouth has the potential to be a great adjunct to student education in terms of mimicking the format of INBDE and encouraging critical thinking by providing hints to guide the student to an answer. However, the inaccuracies of the bot remain a barrier to relying on this form of education.

With any LLM the biggest limitation comes down to the quality of training data. During GPT-4's scrape of the internet, it would have been trained on content with varying levels of quality. This inconsistency could be mitigated through the use of higher quality educational

materials. However, we were limited to open domain and freely available content for our model due to copyright limitations on proprietary material. As this landscape continues to evolve, it is possible that more permissive standards will allow for the incorporation of more content in ChatterMouth’s repository, therefore enhancing its performance. For the time being, this model would best be used in conjunction with a tutor who can catch certain inaccuracies. Furthermore, I can solicit feedback from users on ChatterMouth’s interface and usefulness. I can additionally recruit experts to evaluate the transcripts to assess the bot’s performance.

This experience helped me gain a deeper understanding into how LLMs function and the potential applications in the field of dentistry and education. I foresee the power of LLMs in helping streamline treatment plans based on patient medical history, preferences, and knowledge of past cases. GPTs can be used to enhance personalization through data analysis, automation, and patient engagement. By incorporating previous treatment histories, a GPT may be able to predict outcomes for a patient. As LLM technology rapidly evolves, we can anticipate a growing number of innovative use cases that will be accessible to everyone, not just software engineers.

Table 1:

Name	Principle	Example
Identify GPT	Give the GPT a “role”	“You serve as a dental school professor, tasked with preparing students for the Integrated National Board Dental Examination. Your role involves presenting students with new, different questions that mirror the format and content of the actual INBDE based on the topic requested by the student.”
One Shot Learning	Demonstrate to the bot one clear example you would like it to mimic	I used one-shot learning to create a table format similar to the patient presentation

		<p>on INBDE</p> <p>“Instructions for Table Format:</p> <p>When presenting the patient scenario, format the information as a table with two columns. The first column should list the category of information (e.g., Patient, Chief Complaint, Background/Patient History, Current Findings), and the second column should provide the corresponding details. Here is an example of how to structure this table:</p> <p>Category Information Patient Male, 48 years old Chief Complaint “I’ve been in pain for two days and now my face is swollen.” Background/Patient History Hypertension, Type 2 diabetes, Penicillin allergy Current Findings Facial edema, Lymphadenopathy, Extensive apical radiolucency associated with tooth 6, Temp: 100.3°F, BP: 150/93, Blood glucose: 240 mg/dL”</p>
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RAG Framework	Provides the GPT a relevant, accurate source it can pull from Make sure to use sources that are open to the public and not copyrighted.	I added “Integrated National Board Dental Examination (INBDE) 2024 Candidate Guide” and “Integrated National Board Dental Examination (INBDE) Sample Questions”
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Table 2:

Error	Example	How I Fixed It
Inaccurate Information (Hallucinations) ¹¹	When a question about whether a patient should take Advil or Tylenol after an extraction was posed, the GPT wavered and suggested either could be suitable, rather than providing a concrete answer	Instructed GPT to “first work through the solution based on the provided documents, then compare its solution to the student's response”
Forgetting Instructions	GPT forgets part of instructions such as “do not reveal the correct answer to the student”	Instructed GPT multiple times throughout the prompt to follow the given instruction. Used phrases such as “do NOT reveal the answer in the hint”
Token Limitations	GPT has a set number of “token” so in providing verbose explanations it forgets certain instructions	Instructed the GPT to be as concise as possible

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